

EMBEDDING ENVIRONMENTAL AND CLIMATE ETHICS IN RESEARCH: SIX RECOMMENDATIONS FOR INSTITUTIONS

Who is this for?

This policy brief is intended for academic and research stakeholders responsible for shaping **research ethics and research integrity (RE&RI) governance, support, and education within universities and research institutions.**

These include:

- Research performing organisations leadership and senior management
- Research ethics committees and integrity offices
- Research support staff and managers
- Educators and curriculum developers
- Researchers and postgraduate supervisors

Why now?

Europe's green transition depends on research and innovation. However, most RE&RI frameworks ignore environmental and climate concerns. RE4GREEN's analysis shows that 60% of RE&RI frameworks in the European Research Area make no mention of such issues. Even where they do, guidance is vague and impractical often placing the responsibility on the shoulders of researcher while ignoring institutional accountability. As research increasingly shapes environmental outcomes — from AI to geoengineering — failing to act creates risks. These issues are not abstract or hypothetical. Research has historically contributed to environmental degradation, climate change and social injustice, often reinforcing power asymmetries, extractive practices, and systemic harm. This reality highlights the urgent need to adopt research paradigms grounded in environmental and climate ethics, justice, and precaution. **Ethics must evolve to ensure research supports, not undermines, Europe's climate and sustainability goals.**

What needs to change?

To address these gaps, we recommend **six key actions** to align research ethics with Europe's environmental and climate goals:

1. Integrate environmental and climate ethics into RE&RI policies, guidelines, and frameworks at the institutional level.
2. Integrate environmental and climate ethics into institutional research strategies and agenda-setting processes.
3. Integrate justice-oriented approaches into RE&RI.
4. Strengthen professional training and capacity-building for researchers and ethics committees.
5. Embed environmental and climate ethics into academic education and curriculum development.
6. Operationalise the precautionary principle in institutional research governance.

Policy recommendations

Recommendation 1: Integrate environmental and climate ethics into RE&RI policies, guidelines, and frameworks at the institutional level.

How can institutional RE&RI policies be aligned with Europe's environmental and climate commitments?

- Revise RE&RI policies to include environmental and climate ethics, with clear definitions for concepts like sustainability, environmental and climate justice, and Indigenous rights, while allowing space for multiple worldviews to avoid epistemic domination.
- Identify high-impact, high-risk research areas needing stronger ethical oversight (e.g. geoengineering, AI, critical raw materials and conflict minerals mining, gene editing in biodiversity conservation).
- Align and clarify convergence of ethics governance with EU and global frameworks like the SDGs, Paris Agreement, Green Deal, DNSH, UNDRIP, and Horizon Europe rules and in accordance with UNESCO's [Declaration of Ethical Principles in Relation to Climate Change](#).

Recommendation 2: Integrate environmental and climate ethics into institutional research strategies and agenda-setting processes.

How can institutional research strategies reflect environmental and climate priorities?

- Include environmental and climate ethics considerations into research strategies, resource planning, and priority-setting.
- Establish internal evaluation criteria for research proposals that assess environmental risks, trade-offs, and contributions to environmental and climate goals.
- Foster cross-disciplinary collaboration (e.g., environmental science, engineering, ethics, political theory, law, social anthropology, and social sciences) to guide fair and sustainable transitions.

Recommendation 3: Integrate justice-oriented approaches into RE&RI.

How can RE&RI structures address questions of justice, inclusion, and power?

- Embed justice frameworks — including intergenerational, procedural, epistemic and multispecies justice — into RE&RI governance and recognise and protect Indigenous rights guided by [UNESCO's policy on engaging with indigenous peoples](#).
- Support participatory research with communities affected by environmental degradation and climate change, and by the measures taken to address them (e.g. renewables, carbon capture, resource extraction) while embedding the [CARE Principles](#) (originally developed for Indigenous data governance): Collective benefit, Authority to control, Responsibility, and Ethics.
- Integrate gender-responsive and ecofeminist perspectives to address the gendered impacts of environmental and climate issues and to support intersectional gender justice in research.
- Provide tools such as participatory method guidelines, co-design process templates, justice impact assessment templates, and support structures for inclusive engagement and review.

Recommendation 4: Strengthen professional training and capacity-building for researchers and ethics committees.

How can training and capacity-building better support environmental and climate ethics in research?

- Deliver targeted training on environmental and climate ethics, justice frameworks, and sustainability governance for researchers, support staff and ethics committees.
- Provide practical tools — like case studies, impact templates, and decision-making aids — to support ethical research design and review.
- Build cross-disciplinary capacity by connecting experts across ethics, environmental science, law, social anthropology, policy and other relevant fields to support collaborative learning and informed decision-making across sectors.

Recommendation 5: Embed environmental and climate ethics into academic education and curriculum development.

*How can academic education prepare **learners** to address environmental and climate challenges ethically?*

- Integrate environmental and climate ethics into curricula and RE&RI teaching across all disciplines.
- Create modules on environmental and climate ethics that bridge ethics, sustainability, and innovation also drawing on UNESCO's [LINKS programme](#) to integrate Indigenous and local knowledge.
- Support faculty with resources, incentives, and staff development programmes to update curricula.

Recommendation 6: Operationalise the precautionary principle in institutional research governance.

*How can the **precautionary principle** be embedded in research governance?*

- Require researchers to assess and report potential climatic, environmental and social risks, especially for emerging or experimental technologies.
- Establish ethics committee protocols for applying the [precautionary principle](#), including thresholds for triggering independent review or mitigation plans.
- Promote anticipatory governance approaches that prioritise responsibility, justice, and the avoidance of harm in conditions of uncertainty.

Stakeholder action table

Stakeholder Group	Recommended Actions
➤ Research performing organisations leadership & senior management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Mandate integration of environmental and climate ethics into RE&RI frameworks and research strategies. ✓ Establish policies requiring sustainability and ethics assessments of critical raw materials and conflict minerals used in research and procurement. ✓ Promote interdisciplinary, participatory and just transition-focused research. ✓ Allocate funding and resources to support ethics education and capacity-building. ✓ Mandate environmental and climate ethics to be embedded into existing and future curricula.
➤ Research ethics committees & integrity offices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Include environmental/climate ethics and justice in review protocols and guidelines. ✓ Apply precautionary principle (especially for high-impact/high-risk research). ✓ Work with biosecurity committees to strengthen oversight of research with potential environmental or societal harm.
➤ Research support staff & managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Develop and disseminate tools to support assessment, participation and training. ✓ Organise training sessions for researchers and staff. ✓ Monitor evolving EU compliance requirements and embed them into research support systems.
➤ Educators & curriculum developers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Integrate environmental/climate ethics across disciplines. ✓ Develop new dedicated environmental/climate ethics modules. ✓ Use LINKS and CARE frameworks to incorporate Indigenous and local knowledge.
➤ Researchers & supervisors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Adopt precautionary, participatory, inclusive, and responsible research methods. ✓ Embed ethics into research supervision & evaluation, starting from project design.

Evidence base for the recommendations

Research Ethics and integrity for the GREEN transition (RE4GREEN, <https://re4green.eu/>), a three-year Horizon Europe-funded project, aims to develop a European Research Area framework on ethics and integrity for research and innovation activities that supports the fair and sustainable transition. One of RE4GREEN's main objectives is to analyse the current RE&RI landscape and provide key stakeholders with actionable recommendations on integrating environmental and climate ethics into research and innovation governance.

The recommendations presented in this policy brief are grounded in RE4GREEN's analysis of RE&RI frameworks, guidelines, training programmes & materials and academic literature. The project identified significant gaps and challenges in how environmental and climate ethics are addressed in RE&RI across Europe. Key issues included:

- Systemic governance gaps: Many RE&RI frameworks lack references to climate or environmental ethics, rely too heavily on individual responsibility, and show weak integration of justice-oriented approaches.
- Thematic omissions: Emerging technologies, justice, Indigenous rights, gender perspectives, and ecofeminist approaches are rarely considered in research governance.
- Operational shortcomings: There is limited attention to environmental risk assessment, precaution, and practical guidance. Training on climate and environmental ethics is also scarce.

These gaps highlight the urgent need for structural, institutional, and educational reforms — as outlined in this policy brief.

What's next?

We recognise that the implementation of these recommendations will require time, resources, and institutional commitment. Practical constraints such as staffing, funding, and existing governance processes must be taken into account. This policy brief offers a strategic direction, but each institution must adapt its approach to local realities and capacities. To support the implementation of these recommendations, RE4GREEN is developing operational RE&RI guidelines, to be published in 2026, which will offer practical support for embedding environmental and climate ethics into research governance and practice across institutions.

But guidance alone is not enough. What universities and research institutions choose to prioritise today will shape the role of research in either deepening or preventing environmental harm. We must move beyond statements of intent and avoid 'greenwashing,' transforming instead the foundations of how research is governed, taught, and evaluated. *We have a responsibility to ensure that research does not reproduce the very injustices it aims to address.*

Further reading

1. RE4GREEN. (2025). Mapping environmental and climate ethics in the context of the sustainable transition (Deliverable 1.1). Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No. 101131706. <https://re4green.eu/deliverables/>
2. RE4GREEN. (2025). Gap analysis of research ethics and integrity resources for R&I in general and new climate and environmental technologies in particular (Deliverable 1.3). Horizon Europe, Grant Agreement No. 101131706. <https://re4green.eu/deliverables/>

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Environmental Ethics	A branch of philosophy that considers the moral relationship between humans and the natural world, focusing on responsibilities toward ecosystems, non-human species, and the planet as a whole.
Climate Ethics	A field that examines the ethical dimensions of climate change, including responsibility for emissions, fair distribution of impacts and adaptation burdens, and duties to future generations.
Justice-Oriented Approaches	Research and governance strategies that explicitly address inequalities, power dynamics, and the distribution of risks and benefits, especially in relation to climate and environmental issues.
Climate Justice	A concept that recognises the uneven causes and effects of climate change and seeks equitable solutions, particularly for groups and individuals disproportionately affected by climate impacts.
Environmental Justice	The concept that all people, regardless of race, income, or geography, should have equal protection from environmental harms and equal access to environmental benefits.
Energy Justice	A concept that aims to ensure fair access to energy, equitable distribution of energy costs and benefits, and recognition of affected communities in energy decision-making.
Intergenerational Justice	The concept that current generations have responsibilities toward future generations, particularly in preserving environmental and social conditions that support life and well-being.
Procedural Justice	A dimension of justice concerned with the fairness and inclusiveness of decision-making processes, particularly involving affected or marginalised stakeholders.
Epistemic Justice	The ethical concept emphasising fairness in whose knowledge is valued, included, and recognised in research, especially for historically marginalised groups.
Multispecies Justice	A principle that recognises the rights, interests, and well-being of non-human species, promoting fair and respectful relationships between humans, animals, and ecosystems in research and decision-making.
Indigenous Rights	Legal and moral rights of Indigenous peoples, including the right to self-determination, land, culture, and to be involved in decisions affecting their environments and livelihoods.
Precautionary Principle	An approach to risk management, where, if it is possible that a given policy or action might cause harm to the public or the environment and if there is still no scientific agreement on the issue, the policy or action in question should not be carried out.
High-Impact / High-Risk Research	Research that may have significant environmental, societal, or ethical consequences due to its scale, uncertainty, or the technologies involved (e.g., geoengineering, synthetic biology).
Sustainability (in the research context)	A commitment to conducting and supporting research in ways that meet current needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet theirs, including attention to environmental, social, and economic impacts.
Ecofeminism / Ecofeminist Perspectives	An approach that links ecological concerns with feminist insights, highlighting how systems of domination and exploitation of nature are connected with the oppression of women and marginalised groups.
Do No Significant Harm (DNSH)	An EU principle requiring that research and innovation must not cause significant harm to any of the EU's environmental objectives, such as climate mitigation, biodiversity protection, or pollution reduction.
Participatory Research/Co-design	Research approaches that involve affected communities and stakeholders as active participants in defining research questions, processes, and outcomes.
Emerging Technologies	Technologies that are in early stages of development and may have uncertain, large-scale, or long-term effects on society or the environment (e.g., AI, geoengineering, gene editing).